

A prospective cohort study of HPV-mediated oral and oropharyngeal cancer and efficient detection methods

Zdravka Pashova-Tasseva¹

1 Department of Periodontology, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Medical University-Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Medical University-Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

3 Department of Clinical immunology, University hospital Alexandrovska, Medical University-Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Department of ENT diseases, University hospital St. Anna, Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

5 Department of Maxillofacial Surgery, Pirogov Hospital; Bulgaria., Sofia, Bulgaria

6 FDM, MU – Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

7 Department of Oral and Maxillofacial surgery, Medical University-Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Elitsa Deliverska (elitsadeliverska@yahoo.com)

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Abstract

The role of HPV is accepted in pathogenesis of oral and oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma (OPSCC) .

The aim of this study is to investigate the association between HPV and oral and oropharyngeal carcinoma, to analyze the oncoanatomical localizations and effective detection methods.

We investigated 89 patients-50 patients with histologically proven OPSCC and 39 people as a test group. Samples for HPV detection were taken with smear test and oral rinse of each patient. In 30% of cases with OPSCC we found an association with HPV in the test group. Strains were isolated from samples by PCR method. Combination of oral rinse and brush has the highest HPV detection rate (77.8%). Tumours in oropharynx have a higher risk of HPV infection. In the study, HPV16 was found to be predominant, as well as other strains 51,52,58,66,6,31,39, alone or in combination.

Of important clinical importance is the accurate determination of the HPV status of tumor, which is important for management and prognosis.

Keywords

detection methods, Human papillomavirus, Oral carcinoma, Oropharyngeal Squamous cell carcinoma, prevalence

Introduction

Oral carcinoma ranks among the ten most common malignant diseases worldwide, which emphasizes its importance in the context of public health. Notably, the incidence of oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) in Western Europe and the United States has increased dramatically over the past two decades (Chaturvedi et al. 2011; Roman and Aragones 2021). In 2020, 94,412 new cases of (OSCC) and 48,143 deaths worldwide were registered (Sung et al. 2021; Khan et al. 2025).

This increase in incidence is largely due to human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, as the incidence of HPV-mediated OPSCC (HPV + OPC) has increased but with clear geographic variations (Mehanna et al. 2013, 2016; Van Dyne et al. 2015).

In Bulgaria for 2020, the incidence is 3.3/100,000, with a difference between the sexes, respectively 5.0/100,000 in men and 1.7/100,000 in women (Ferlay et al. 2020). There is also high variability in the incidence of infection by anatomical location (Yete et al. 2018). HPV-mediated oropharyngeal cancer is a distinct disease entity with distinct epidemiological and molecular features and biological behaviour and is characterized by better response to treatment and survival than HPV-unrelated oropharyngeal cancer (Ang et al. 2010; Lechner et al. 2022; Jung et al. 2010).

Oncogenesis in HPV-associated cancers is mediated by viral oncoproteins E6 and E7, which inhibit the tumor suppressor proteins p53 and retinoblastoma (Rb) protein, respectively (Hebner and Laimins 2006; Lechner et al. 2022). In contrast, HPV-negative HNSCC is due to DNA damage by carcinogens with subsequent mutations in tumor suppressor genes such as TP53 and CDKN2A (Khan et al. 2025).

Given the prognostic advantage of HPV-related oropharyngeal cancer, the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) and the Union for International Cancer Control (UICC) (UICC) developed separate classifications for HPV-related and non-HPV-related diseases in the new TNM 8th edition staging system (TNM 8) for HPV-related oropharyngeal cancer (Craig et al. 2019).

Data on the prevalence of HPV in the oral cavity are important for several reasons – to understand the profile of the tumor lesion – HPV positive or negative, as HPV positives have a better prognosis; to define risk groups; to be used as a measure of the results and efficacy of vaccination programs. Therefore, various effective and non-invasive methods of research are sought (Chaturvedi et al. 2011; Craig et al. 2019; De Martel et al. 2020).

HPV mediation of oropharyngeal cancer can be established by testing for the presence of HPV DNA or mRNA in the tumor using PCR-based methods or in-situ hybridization (ISH). Overexpression of the p16 protein serves as an excellent surrogate biomarker for HPV causation in OPSCC (Smeets et al. 2007; Tang et al. 2020). The positive prognosis is also more pronounced in HPV-positive patients who are also p16 positive (Mehanna et al. 2023).

The world literature discusses conventional methods for HPV detection (p16 immunohistochemistry, HPV

DNA ISH, HPV DNA PCR, HPV E6/E7 mRNA RT-PCR, HPV RNA ISH, as well as emerging new approaches (HPV circulating tumor DNA, HPV16 E6 antibodies, oral HPV DNA/mRNA PCR, NGS). Currently, a combined testing approach using sequential screening with p16 immunohistochemistry and confirmation with HPV DNA PCR is preferred by many authors (Smeets et al. 2007; Tang et al. 2020; Mehanna et al. 2023). HPV RNA in-situ hybridization could potentially serve as a single test due to its good sensitivity and specificity, but is not routinely used (Jung et al. 2010; Mena et al. 2022; Khan et al. 2025).

The use of liquid biopsies such as HPV circulating tumor DNA could be successfully used for early detection of HPV-associated oropharyngeal carcinomas. HPV16 E6 antibodies and oral HPV DNA PCR can be used as additional tests to aid diagnosis (Tang et al. 2020; Mehanna et al. 2023). However, there are limitations to the use of PCR for HPV DNA detection – the test can be very sensitive; it is impossible to distinguish whether HPV DNA detected by this method is from malignant tumor tissue or the virus is only present in adjacent, non-neoplastic tissues. Detection of HPV DNA by PCR, like DNA ISH, does not provide information on whether the virus is transcriptionally active. To address this question, several studies have shown that reverse transcription PCR can be used on formalin-fixed specimens to detect E6 and E7 mRNA transcripts, although this method is not currently available for clinical use and has not been compared with other methodologies (van Houten et al. 2001; Smeets et al. 2007; Palve et al. 2018; Tang et al. 2020; Mehanna et al. 2023; Hillier et al. 2025; Khan et al. 2025).

It is assumed that to be biologically and clinically relevant, HPV must be transcriptionally active, and some investigators have suggested that detection of HPV RNA should be the gold standard for HPV testing. For example, patients with HPV DNA+/RNA+ have improved overall survival compared with those with HPV DNA+/RNA- (Jung et al. 2010).

In the dynamic environment of new tests and developments in molecular biology, clinicians must have access to and choose cost-effective, accurate, and effective HPV tests, as there is still no standard for HPV virus detection.

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between HPV and oral and oropharyngeal carcinoma, to analyze the oncoanatomical localizations, and to discuss effective detection methods.

Design of the study

This study represents a centralized analysis of individual data for patients diagnosed with oral and oropharyngeal carcinoma based on data from three hospitals in Sofia, Bulgaria.

Material and methods

A total of 89 subjects participated in the study – 50 cancer patients and 39 healthy controls. All participants agreed to participate in the study and signed an informed consent.

The patients were recruited from Alexandrovska Hospital, Pirogov Hospital and St. Anna Hospital in Sofia, while healthy volunteers were randomly selected.

A clinical questionnaire was prepared for the patient and the treating team of doctors to fill in information – information on age, gender, tobacco use and use of electronic cigarettes and alcohol; TNM 7th edition staging; comorbidity; local oral status in relation to the presence of periodontal disease and local irritants, location of the lesion, biological behaviour of lesion, clinical characteristic of lesion, and histopathological findings.

Inclusion criteria were a patient with histologically verified primary oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma. Patients underwent imaging (CT or MRI) and histological confirmation by biopsy – formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissue. Patients were treated with surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy or a combination of these, or were referred for palliative treatment.

HPV testing was performed using oral rinse and oral brush samples for HPV DNA PCR detection. – oral rinse 15 – to 30-second rinsing/swishing, followed by 15 – to 30-second gargling. Brush samples are taken from the area of the tumor lesion. Samples were collected from all participants in the study using pre-defined protocols by the treating clinicians and stored and transported according to strict guidelines.

In the collected samples, genotyping and quantification of HPV were performed by multiplex Real Time PCR using validated commercial kits HPV Quant 21 on the test group – 50 patients with oropharyngeal carcinoma and on the healthy controls – 39. Multiplex serologic testing was performed at Department of Microbiology – Faculty of Medicine – MU – Sofia. Kits for Real-Time PCR quantitative detection and genotyping of 21 HPV genotypes were used, including high-risk 16, 18, 26, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 53, 56, 58, 59, 66, 68, 73, 82 and low-risk 6, 11 and 44 .

Molecular methods for HPV detection, specifically PCR-based viral DNA assays in our study were performed using oral rinse and brush biopsy test samples in our study is consistent with molecular methods for HPV detection, specifically PCR-based assays for viral DNA. These noninvasive approaches are suitable for identifying the presence of HPV in exfoliated oral epithelial cells and saliva, although they do not distinguish between transcriptionally active infections, but they allow us to compare the results of the two methods and determine which is more accurate.

Database, ethics approval and consent to participate

This study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained for patients diagnosed in 2024–2025. A standardized Microsoft Excel form was used to collect and harmonize data. Ethics approval of the study was obtained by the ethics committee (KENIMUS) of the Medical University – Sofia. No. 03/23.02.2024., ethic approval date – №985-29/02/2024.

Statistical analysis

SPSS (Statistical Program for Statistics) was used to process the data from the study. Package for the Social Sciences) was version 20.0.

1. Descriptive statistics

– Quantitative variables are represented by summary statistical characteristics – arithmetic mean (Mean), standard deviation (SD); minimum and maximum value.

– Categorical variables are represented by absolute (N) and relative (%) frequencies.

2. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to check the shape of frequency distributions for quantitative variables.

3. Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test – when examining relationships between descriptive (categorical) data with two or more categories.

4. T-test – when comparing two independent groups when the distribution of the variable under study is normal.

The adopted significance level is $\alpha=0.05$. Statistical significance is accepted when the p value is less than α ($p < 0.05$).

Results

The results of our study show that the average age of patients with HPV positive (+) is 60 years, and HPV negative (-) is 62 years. No statistically significant relationship was observed (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean age of patients with OSCC carcinoma depending on HPV status.

	HPV status	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	p
Age	No	35	61.97	10.93	38.00	83.00	0.783
	Yes	15	60.17	10.15	44.00	78.00	

Males are more affected, accounting for 80% of patients, with nearly 1/3 for HPV (+).

Table 2. Distribution of patients by gender depending on HPV status.

	Gender	HPV status		Total	p
		No	Yes		
Male	N	29	11	40	0.462
	%	82.9%	73.3%		
Female	N	6	4	10	
	%	17.1%	26.7%		

In our study 70% of the test group – patients with OSCC – were HPV (-), while in the control group 95% were HPV (-). In 12% of the test group more than one strain was detected (Table 3).

Table 3. HPV status in test group and control group.

Groups	HPV status	N	%
Patients with OSSC	HPV (-)	35	70.0
	1 strain	9	18.0
	More than 1 strain	6	12.0
	Total	50	100.0
Control group	HPV (-)	37	94.9
	strain	2	5.1
	Total	39	100.0

In the conducted study, HPV16 was predominantly found both alone and in combination with other strains – 51, 52, 58, 66, 6, 31, 39 (Table 4) $n=1.0717$ close to statistical significance. It is interesting that other strains were also found both alone – HPV 6 and in combination – HPV 39 and 58. In the control group – 5.1% positive for HPV, only single strains were found – HPV16 and 51.

Table 4. HPV strains in test group and control group.

Group	HPV status	N	%
Test group	No	35	70.0
	16	8	16.0
	16;51;66	1	2.0
	16;52	1	2.0
	16;6	1	2.0
	16;6;31	1	2.0
	39;58	2	4.0
	6	1	2.0
	Total	50	100.0
	Control group	No	37
16		1	2.6
51		1	2.6
Total		39	100.0

The oncoanatomical localization of the studied patients (Fig. 1) from the test group shows that 20% of the patients have carcinoma of the tongue and 34% have carcinoma of the larynx, 10% have floor of the mouth, 8% have localization of the tongue and floor of the mouth, and 10% have pharyngeal involvement. In 22% of the patients, involvement of more than one oncoanatomical area was found.

Figure 1. Oncoanatomical localization of OSSC.

The results of our study show that pharynx carcinomas are HPV (+) in a higher percentage of cases, as well as pharynx and root of the tongue, without a statistically significant relationship. Regarding the oral cavity, the floor of the mouth and tongue are more affected, but again without a statistically significant relationship, but weakly expressed trends are visible. In the localization of carcinoma-larynx, over half of the cases are HPV (-). In 25 cases with the floor of the mouth involved, the carcinoma is negative for HPV in isolation or in various combinations, in 4 cases it is HPV (+). In all other localizations, 25 cases are HPV negative and 11 are HPV positive without a statistically significant relationship.

In the 50 cases of malignant tumors in different areas of the oral cavity, larynx and pharynx studied, HPV was not detected in most cases (70%, 35/50), HPV positives were in a total 30% (15/50). Detection was found in: 1 HPV strain in 9 cases (18%) and more than 1 HPV strain in 6 cases (12%) (Table 5, Fig. 2). This means that most tumors do not contain HPV, but in some patients the virus is present, which may be a factor in the development of the disease.

Distribution by localization in the study as the most commonly affected area is the Larynx – 17 cases (34% of all), with 29% of them being HPV positive. The second most common is Tongue – 10 cases (20%), half of which are HPV positive. Other more common locations: Floor of the mouth – 5 cases (40% HPV positive), Pharynx – 5 cases (60% HPV positive).

Locations with the highest HPV frequency.

At 100% HPV positivity (all cases tested positive): it is found that by localization – Gingiva/Floor of mouth/Tongue (1 case, >1 strain), Floor of mouth/Tongue (2 cases, 1 strain) and Pharynx/Tongue (1 case, >1 strain).

Although the number of cases in these groups is small, the complete HPV positivity suggests a strong association between this anatomical combination and HPV infection.

In the oral cavity, HPV is probably not a major factor in tumor development.

The conclusions that can be made are that localizations that involve the tongue or pharynx have a higher risk of HPV infection. This is supported by the high positivity rates. The larynx is the most commonly affected area, but

Table 5. Oncoanatomical localization of OSSC and HPV status.

Oncoanatomical localization of OSSC		HPV status		Total
		No	Yes	
Gingiva/buccal mucosa	N	1	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	2.0%
Gingiva/ hard palate	N	1	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	2.0%
Gingiva/floor of the mouth	N	1	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	2.0%
Gingiva/floor of the mouth /tongue	N	0	1	1
	%	0.0%	6.7%	2.0%
Tongue	N	8	2	10
	%	22.9%	13.3%	20.0%
Tongue/floor of the mouth	N	4	0	4
	%	11.4%	0.0%	8.0%
Larynx	N	12	5	17
	%	34.3%	33.3%	34.0%
Hard palate	N	1	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	2.0%
Floor of the mouth	N	3	2	5
	%	8.6%	13.3%	10.0%
Floor of the mouth/buccal mucosa	N	1	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	2.0%
Floor of the mouth/tongue	N	0	1	1
	%	0.0%	6.7%	2.0%
Floor of the mouth/tongue/palate	N	1	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	2.0%
Pharynx	N	2	3	5
	%	5.7%	20.0%	10.0%
Pharynx/tongue	N	0	1	1
	%	0.0%	6.7%	2.0%
Total	N	35	15	50
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

not always associated with HPV (most are HPV negative). In combined anatomical areas (e.g. Tongue + Pharynx) the incidence of HPV is higher. More than 1 HPV strain is less common (only 12%), but is often found in areas with a more aggressive tumor profile (pharynx, tongue) (Table 6, Fig. 3).

Locations such as the gingiva and palate are less associated with HPV and other factors probably play a greater role there (smoking, alcohol, etc.).

The oncoanatomic location as Gingiva/Floor of mouth/Tongue, Floor of mouth/Tongue, and Pharynx/Tongue all have 100% HPV positivity, while several locations have 0%.

Table 6. HPV strains in different oncoanatomical locations.

Oncoanatomical localization		HPV finding			Total
		No finding	1 strain	More than 1 strain	
Gingiva/buccal mucosa	N	1	0	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Gingiva/Palate	N	1	0	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Gingiva/Floor of mouth	N	1	0	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Gingiva/Floor of mouth/Tongue	N	0	0	1	1
	%	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%	2.0%
Language	N	8	2	0	10
	%	22.9%	22.2%	0.0%	20.0%
Tongue/Floor of mouth	N	4	0	0	4
	%	11.4%	0.0%	0.0%	8.0%
Larynx	N	12	4	1	17
	%	34.3%	44.4%	16.7%	34.0%
Palate	N	1	0	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Floor of the mouth	N	3	1	1	5
	%	8.6%	11.1%	16.7%	10.0%
Floor of mouth/buccal mucosa	N	1	0	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Floor of mouth/Tongue	N	0	1	0	1
	%	0.0%	11.1%	0.0%	2.0%
Floor of mouth/Tongue/Palate	N	1	0	0	1
	%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%
Pharynx	N	2	1	2	5
	%	5.7%	11.1%	33.3%	10.0%
Pharynx/Tongue	N	0	0	1	1
	%	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%	2.0%
Total	N	35	9	6	50
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 2. Oncoanatomical localization of OSSC and HPV status.

Figure 3. The percentage of HPV-positive cases for each tumor location.

In our study, it was found that the predominant localization of the pharynx and larynx demonstrated a higher frequency of HPV (+) – in 11 patients HPV (+) carcinoma was detected, with 7 cases having one strain, and 4 cases having more than one strain (Table 7).

Combination patients of oral rinse and brush has the highest detection rate of HPV (77.8%). And with statistical significance of the results (Table 8, Fig. 4). And oral rinse and brush test separately detect HPV in about 61% of cases, but the combined method increases the likelihood of detecting more than one strain. In the case of a pap smear in the oral cavity, 2 cases (40%) were diagnosed, and in the upper respiratory tract 3 cases (60%). The same ratio was observed in a mouthwash sample. When using both methods together, cases were identified only in the upper

Figure 4. Comparison of HPV detection methods in patients with OSSC.

Table 7. HPV status in oral cavity carcinoma and pharyngeal and laryngeal carcinoma.

Localization		N	HPV status			Total	p
			Negative	1 strain	More than one strain		
Oral mucosa	N	21	2	2	25	0.104	
		60.0%	22.2%	33.3%	50.0%		
	Pharyngeal/laryngeal cancer	N	14	7	4		25
		%	40.0%	77.8%	66.7%		50.0%

Table 8. Comparison of HPV detection methods in patients with OSSC.

Group	Sample		N	HPV status			Total	p
				HPV(-)	HPV(+) 1 strain	HPV(+) More than 1 strain		
Test group	Sample	No	N	35	0	0	35	<0.001
			%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	70.0%	
			N	0	4	1	5	
			%	0.0%	44.4%	16.7%	10.0%	
		Combined method (brush test and oral rinse)	N	0	4	1	5	
			%	0.0%	44.4%	16.7%	10.0%	
			N	0	1	4	5	
			%	0.0%	11.1%	66.7%	10.0%	
Control group	Sample	No	N	37	0	0	37	0.001
			%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	94.9%	
		Brush test	N	0	2	0	2	
			%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	5.1%	

respiratory tract – 5 cases (100%). For greater accuracy, we recommend combining the two HPV detection tests.

In summary, the results highlight the importance of HPV as an etiological factor in oropharyngeal and oral lesions, which may have serious and important diagnostic, clinical and therapeutic implications.

Discussion

Human papillomavirus (HPV)-positive oral and oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinomas (OSCCs) exhibit distinct molecular characteristics compared to their HPV-negative counterparts. A marked geographic heterogeneity in HPV-attributable fractions (HPV-AFs) across head and neck cancers (HNCs), particularly in oropharyngeal carcinoma (OPC), has been consistently reported (Mehanna et al. 2013, 2016; Anantharaman et al. 2017; Algudaibi et al. 2021). Within this context, our study provides an updated assessment of the epidemiological profile of HPV-associated OPC in the Bulgarian population.

In our cohort, the mean age of HPV-positive patients was 60 years, compared to 62 years for HPV-negative patients. This difference was not statistically significant, and our findings align with those of other investigators who reported similar age distributions (Rettig et al. 2018a, b; Windon et al. 2018). These observations challenge the earlier perception that HPV-positive OPC predominantly affects younger individuals and instead highlight an increasing prevalence among older patients, a trend that has also been linked to less favorable survival outcomes. Conversely, several studies have documented a higher incidence of HPV-positive OPC in younger populations (Gillison et al. 2008; Ang et al. 2010; Mehanna et al. 2013; Mena et al. 2020), suggesting potential population – and region-specific differences.

Regarding sex distribution, our findings confirm the predominance of males, with 80% of cases occurring in men, irrespective of HPV status. This male predominance has also been consistently documented in previous epidemiological studies (D'Souza et al. 2007; Gillison et al. 2015).

Globally, HPV is estimated to account for approximately 25–30% of OPCs, compared with only 2–4% of oral cavity carcinomas and 2–4% of laryngeal carcinomas (Alemay and Mena 2021; Algudaibi et al. 2021; Roman and Aragonés 2021; Mena et al. 2022).

Analysis of the oncoanatomical distribution of tumors in the study group revealed that 20% of patients presented with carcinoma of the tongue, 34% with carcinoma of the larynx, 10% with carcinoma of the floor of the mouth, 8% with combined involvement of the tongue and floor of the mouth, and 10% with pharyngeal carcinoma. In 22% of cases, more than one anatomical site was affected. These findings are consistent with previous reports showing that approximately 30% of new cases involve oropharyngeal carcinoma (OPC), compared with 2.1% of oral cavity carcinoma (OC) and 2.3% of laryngeal carcinoma (LC) (Chaturvedi et al. 2011; De Martel et al. 2020; Mena et al. 2022). Moreover, HPV-positive OPC remains substantially more common in males, a trend repeatedly confirmed across multiple large-

scale studies (Gillison et al. 2015; Mena et al. 2020; Lechner et al. 2022; Fonsêca et al. 2023; Mehanna et al. 2023).

The present study further highlights the prevalence of HPV in lesions localized to the oral cavity, oropharynx, and larynx. These findings are consistent with international evidence supporting HPV as a key risk factor in the development of malignant and premalignant lesions across these anatomical regions. In our cohort, HPV positivity was most frequently observed in oropharyngeal carcinomas, in line with global trends. Within the oral cavity, the floor of the mouth and tongue were more commonly affected; however, these differences did not reach statistical significance, though weakly expressed trends could be observed. In contrast, more than half of laryngeal carcinomas were HPV negative. Specifically, among 25 cases involving the floor of the mouth, carcinoma – whether isolated or in combination with other localizations – was HPV negative in the majority, with only 4 cases testing HPV positive.

The higher frequency of HPV in oropharyngeal lesions likely reflects a greater propensity for viral integration and malignant transformation in this region. This may be explained by distinct features of the immune microenvironment and site-specific tissue characteristics, which appear to facilitate viral attachment and persistence to a greater extent than in the oral epithelium.

When comparing the localization of HPV-positive lesions between the oral cavity and oropharynx, our data indicate that, although HPV is less frequent in the oral cavity, its presence is clinically relevant and should not be overlooked. This underscores the importance of incorporating routine HPV testing into the diagnostic algorithm for patients with oral neoplasia, particularly in light of the rising incidence of HPV-associated OPC observed globally over the past two decades (Chaturvedi et al. 2011; Palve et al. 2018; Mena et al. 2022; Fonsêca et al. 2023).

Another key consideration is the role of different HPV genotypes, as high-risk types such as HPV16 are strongly associated with more aggressive disease and poorer prognosis (Mehanna et al. 2019). In our study, 70% of patients in the test group with OSCC were HPV negative, compared with 95% in the control group. Interestingly, 12% of test group patients harbored multiple HPV strains. Although our sample size was limited, we identified multiple strains in cases of laryngeal carcinoma, floor of the mouth carcinoma, and pharyngeal carcinoma.

HPV16 was the most commonly detected genotype, found both alone and in combination with other strains, including HPV51, HPV52, HPV66, HPV6, and HPV31. Additional strains such as HPV6, HPV39, and HPV58 were also identified, either individually or in combination. In contrast, only single strains – HPV16 and HPV51 – were detected in the control group. Notably, pharyngeal and laryngeal carcinomas demonstrated the highest rates of HPV positivity in our series: HPV-positive tumors were identified in 11 patients, of whom seven carried a single strain and four had multiple strains. Nevertheless, the laryngeal epithelium is generally regarded as less susceptible to HPV infection, owing to anatomical and immunological barriers (D'Souza et al. 2007; Roman and Aragonés 2021; Mena et al. 2022).

The genotypic profile observed in our study largely parallels patterns reported internationally, where HPV31, HPV33, and HPV52 frequently emerge as additional oncogenic strains (van Houten et al. 2001; Gillison et al. 2008; Mehanna et al. 2016; Schache et al. 2016). While we did not detect HPV18 or HPV33 in our cohort, we identified other oncogenic types such as HPV51, HPV66, HPV6, HPV39, and HPV58. This diversity emphasizes the ubiquity of HPV and reinforces the necessity of effective preventive strategies, including vaccination, to reduce the burden of HPV-associated malignancies (Bhatia et al. 2015; Mehanna et al. 2019; Tsentemidou et al. 2021).

From a clinical standpoint, the identification of HPV-positive lesions has a direct impact on therapeutic decision-making and patient follow-up (Fakhry et al. 2008). HPV-positive oropharyngeal carcinomas, for instance, are characterized by an enhanced response to radiotherapy and chemotherapy, which translates into improved overall survival rates (Brenner et al. 2020).

Accurate detection and genotyping of HPV strains are therefore crucial for diagnosis, prognosis, and long-term management of patients with HPV-related lesions. A variety of laboratory methods are currently employed in clinical practice, each with distinct advantages and limitations in terms of sensitivity, specificity, complexity, and applicability. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) remains one of the most widely used approaches, offering high sensitivity and the capacity to detect both general HPV presence and individual genotypes. In our study, we employed PCR, including multiplex PCR, which enables the simultaneous detection of multiple HPV types – a valuable advantage in tumors with potential coinfection. Two types of samples were analyzed, tumor tissue obtained by brush sampling and oral rinse specimens. Our findings demonstrated a statistically significant advantage of using both approaches in combination, yielding the most reliable and accurate results. The choice of diagnostic method continues to be debated in the literature, with increasing interest in non-invasive, highly sensitive approaches. While PCR is rapid and sensitive, it does not provide information regarding viral integration. Immunohistochemistry (IHC) for p16 is cost-effective and simple yet lacks specificity. In situ hybridization (ISH) offers localization of viral DNA but is technically more demanding and costly. Next-generation sequencing (NGS) represents the most informative tool, capable of identifying integration events and viral variants, though it requires substantial resources and technical expertise (Gillison et al. 2008; Tang et al. 2020; Hillier et al. 2025). Based on our results, we conclude that combined brush and oral rinse sampling with PCR provides a practical, sensitive, and feasible strategy that could be integrated into diagnostic and screening protocols.

Despite these promising findings, several limitations of our study must be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size and the diagnostic methods applied restrict the generalizability of our conclusions. Future research should focus on larger and more heterogeneous populations, employing more advanced molecular techniques to improve HPV detection and characterization.

Given the sensitivity of HPV-driven tumors to immune-mediated mechanisms, novel therapeutic strategies such as immunotherapy and molecularly targeted therapies hold considerable promises for improving patient prognosis and survival (Wakeham et al. 2019).

In conclusion, our study reinforces the pivotal role of HPV in the pathogenesis of lesions of the oral cavity and oropharynx and highlights the necessity of an integrated diagnostic and therapeutic approach that incorporates HPV status assessment. Such strategies will facilitate more effective prevention, provide a more accurate prognosis, and support the development of personalized treatment regimens.

Conclusion

HPV-mediated oral and oropharyngeal carcinomas have different pathogenesis and a better prognosis than HPV-negative oropharyngeal carcinomas, which affect staging and prognosis. Therefore, accurate determination of the HPV status of the tumor lesion is of important clinical importance, especially in oropharyngeal carcinomas.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: An ethics statement was conducted in full accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki. The study was approved by The Institutional Ethic Committee of Medical University - Sofia, KENIMUS. No. 03/23.02.2024., ethic approval date- №985-29/02/2024.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Medical University- Sofia

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

All authors had full access to the data in the study and took responsibility for the integrity of the data and the accuracy of the data analysis.

Author ORCIDs

Zdravka Pashova-Tasseva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2635-083X>

Vessela Raykova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9199-9600>

Milena Ivanova-Shivarova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4128-9915>

Stanislav Yordanov <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9145-7235>

Svetoslav Slavkov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9088-5532>

Daniel Markov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9169-6987>

Viktor Lenkov <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8164-7559>

Elitsa Deliverska <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2356-9932>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Alemanly L, Mena M (2021) HPV attributable fractions and trends in head and neck carcinomas. HPVWorld. <https://www.hpvworld.com> [accessed 14 Aug 2025]
- Algudaibi LY, AlMeaigel S, AlQahtani N, Shaheen NA, Aboalela A (2021) Oral and oropharyngeal cancer: knowledge, attitude and practices among medical and dental practitioners. *Cancer Reports* 4(4): e1349. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cnr2.1349>
- Anantharaman D, Abedi-Ardekani B, Beachler DC, Gheit T, Olshan AF, Wisniewski K, Wunsch-Filho V, Toporcov TN, Tajara EH, Levi JE, Moyses RA, Boccia S, Cadoni G, Rindi G, Ahrens W, Merletti F, Conway DI, Wright S, Carreira C, Renard H, Chopard P, McKay-Chopin S, Scelo G, Tommasino M, Brennan P, D'Souza G (2017) Geographic heterogeneity in the prevalence of human papillomavirus in head and neck cancer. *International Journal of Cancer* 140(9): 1968–1975. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.30608>
- Ang KK, Harris J, Wheeler R, Weber R, Rosenthal DI, Nguyen-Tân PF, Westra WH, Chung CH, Jordan RC, Lu C, Kim H, Axelrod R, Silverman CC, Redmond KP, Gillison ML (2010) Human papillomavirus and survival of patients with oropharyngeal cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine* 363(1): 24–35. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa0912217>
- Bhatia A, Burtneis B (2015) Human papillomavirus-associated oropharyngeal cancer: defining risk groups and clinical trials. *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 33(29): 3243–3250. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2015.61.2358>
- Brenner N, Mentzer AJ, Hill M, Almond R, Allen N, Pawlita M, Waterboer T (2020) Characterization of human papillomavirus (HPV) 16 E6 seropositive individuals without HPV-associated malignancies after 10 years of follow-up in the UK Biobank. *EBioMedicine* 62: e103123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2020.103123>
- Chaturvedi AK, Engels EA, Pfeiffer RM, Hernandez BY, Xiao W, Kim E, Jiang B, Goodman MT, Sibug-Saber M, Cozen W, Liu L, Lynch CF, Wentzensen N, Jordan RC, Altekruse S, Anderson WF, Rosenberg PS, Gillison ML (2011) Human papillomavirus and rising oropharyngeal cancer incidence in the United States. *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 29(32): 4294–4301. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2011.36.4596>
- Craig SG, Anderson LA, Schache AG, Moran M, Graham L, Currie K, Rooney K, Robinson M, Upile NS, Brooker R, Mesri M, Bingham V, McQuaid S, Jones T, McCance DJ, Salto-Tellez M, McDade SS, James JA (2019) Recommendations for determining HPV status in patients with oropharyngeal cancers under TNM8 guidelines: a two-tier approach. *British Journal of Cancer* 120(8): 827–833. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41416-019-0414-9>
- De Martel C, Georges D, Bray F, Ferlay J, Clifford GM (2020) Global burden of cancer attributable to infections in 2018: A worldwide incidence analysis. *Lancet Global Health* 8(2): e180–e190. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(19\)30488-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30488-7)
- D'Souza G, Kreimer AR, Viscidi R, Pawlita M, Fakhry C, Koch WM, Westra WH, Gillison ML (2007) Case-control study of human papillomavirus and oropharyngeal cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine* 356(19): 1944–1956. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa065497>
- Fakhry C, Westra WH, Li S, Cmelak A, Ridge JA, Pinto H, Forastiere A, Gillison ML (2008) Improved survival of patients with human papillomavirus-positive head and neck squamous cell carcinoma in a prospective clinical trial. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute* 100(4): 261–269. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djn011>
- Ferlay J, Ervik M, Lam F, Colombet M, Mery L, Piñeros M, Znaor A, Soerjomataram I, Bray F (2020) Global Cancer Observatory: Cancer Today. International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, France. <https://gco.iarc.fr/today> [accessed 10 Oct 2023]
- Fonseca TC, Jural LA, Marañón-Vásquez GA, Magno MB, Roza ALOC, Ferreira DMTP, Maia LC, Romañach MJ, Agostini M, Abrahão AC (2023) Global prevalence of human papillomavirus-related oral and oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinomas: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clinical Oral Investigations* 28(1): e62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-023-05425-0>
- Gillison ML, D'Souza G, Westra W, Sugar E, Xiao W, Begum S, Viscidi R (2008) Distinct risk factor profiles for human papillomavirus type 16-positive and human papillomavirus type 16-negative head and neck cancers. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute* 100(6): 407–420. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djn025>
- Gillison ML, Chaturvedi AK, Anderson WF, Fakhry C (2015) Epidemiology of human papillomavirus-positive head and neck squamous cell carcinoma. *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 33(29): 3235–3242. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2015.61.6995>
- Hillier B, Waterboer T, Brooks J, Nankivell P, Agarwal R, Abou-Foul AK, Fulton-Lieuw T, Kristunas C, Vorsters A, Parish J, Mehanna H (2025) Efficacy of oral rinse and other detection methods in detecting oral human papillomavirus infections: the Oromouth cohort study. *Journal of Infection* 90(3): e106438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2025.106438>
- Hebner CM, Laimins LA (2006) Human papillomaviruses: basic mechanisms of pathogenesis and oncogenicity. *Reviews in Medical Virology* 16(2): 83–97. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rmv.488>
- Jung AC, Briolat J, Millon R, de Reynies A, Rickman D, Thomas E, Abecassis J, Clavel C, Wasyluk B (2010) Biological and clinical relevance of transcriptionally active human papillomavirus infection in oropharynx squamous cell carcinoma. *International Journal of Cancer* 126(8): 1882–1894. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.24911>

- Khan A, Pillay M, Bipath R, Msimang M, Harry J, Sibiyi AL, Msomi N (2025) Evolution of testing for the diagnosis of human papillomavirus (HPV) status in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma: where from and where to? *Oral Oncology* 162: e107208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oraloncology.2025.107208>
- Lechner M, Liu J, Masterson L, Fenton TR (2022) HPV-associated oropharyngeal cancer: epidemiology, molecular biology and clinical management. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology* 19(5): 306–327. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-022-00603-7>
- Mehanna H, Beech T, Nicholson T, El-Hariry I, McConkey C, Paleri V, Roberts S (2013) Prevalence of human papillomavirus in oropharyngeal and nonoropharyngeal head and neck cancer: systematic review and meta-analysis of trends by time and region. *Head & Neck* 35(5): 747–755. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hed.22015>
- Mehanna H, Franklin N, Compton N, Robinson M, Powell N, Biswas-Baldwin N, Paleri V, Hartley A, Fresco L, Al-Booz H, Junor E, El-Hariry I, Roberts S, Harrington K, Ang KK, Dunn J, Woodman C (2016) Geographic variation in human papillomavirus-related oropharyngeal cancer: data from four multinational randomized trials. *Head & Neck* 38(S1): E1863–E1869. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hed.24336>
- Mehanna H, Bryant TS, Babrah J, Louie K, Bryant JL, Spruce RJ, Batis N, Olaley O, Jones J, Struijk L, Molijn A, Vorsters A, Rosillon D, Taylor S, D'Souza G (2019) Human papillomavirus vaccine effectiveness and potential herd immunity for reducing oncogenic oropharyngeal HPV-16 prevalence in the United Kingdom: a cross-sectional study. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 69(8): 1296–1302. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciy1081>
- Mehanna H, Taberna M, von Buchwald C, Tous S, Brooks J, Mena M, Morey F, Grønhoj C, Rasmussen JH, Garset-Zamani M, Bruni L, Batis N, Brakenhoff RH, Leemans CR, Baatenburg de Jong RJ, Klusmann JP, Wuerdemann N, Wagner S, Dalianis T, Marklund L, Mirghani H, Schache A, James JA, Huang SH, O'Sullivan B, Nankivell P, Broglie MA, Hoffmann M, Quabius ES, Alemany L, HNCIG-EPIC group (2023) Prognostic implications of p16 and HPV discordance in oropharyngeal cancer (HNCIG-EPIC-OPC): A multicentre, multinational, individual patient data analysis. *Lancet Oncology* 24(3): 239–251. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(23\)00013-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(23)00013-X)
- Mena M, Frias-Gomez J, Taberna M, Quirós B, Marquez S, Clavero O, Baena A, Lloveras B, Alejo M, León X, García J, Mesía R, Bermejo O, Bonfill T, Aguila A, Guix M, Hijano R, Pavón MA, Torres M, Tous S, Cléries R, Alemany L (2020) Epidemiology of human papillomavirus-related oropharyngeal cancer in a classically low-burden region of southern Europe. *Scientific Reports* 10: e13219. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-70118-7>
- Mena M, Wang X, Tous S, Quirós B, Clavero O, Alejo M, Morey F, Taberna M, Vintro XL, Lloveras Rubio B, Alos L, Mehanna H, Quint W, Pawlita M, Tommasino M, Pavón MA, Muñoz N, De Sanjose S, Bosch FX, Alemany L (2022) Concordance of p16INK4a and E6*1 mRNA among HPV-DNA-positive oropharyngeal, laryngeal, and oral cavity carcinomas from the ICO International Study. *Cancers* 14(15): e3787. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14153787>
- Palve V, Bagwan J, Krishnan NM, Pareek M, Chandola U, Suresh A, Siddappa G, James BL, Kekatpure V, Kuriakose MA, Panda B (2018) Detection of high-risk human papillomavirus in oral cavity squamous cell carcinoma using multiple analytes and their role in patient survival. *JCO Global Oncology* 4: 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JGO.18.00058>
- Rettig EM, Fakhry C, Khararjian A, Westra WH (2018a) Age profile of patients with oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma. *JAMA Otolaryngology–Head & Neck Surgery* 144(5): 431–436. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaoto.2018.0310>
- Rettig EM, Zaidi M, Faraji F, Eisele DW, El Asmar M, Fung N, D'Souza G, Fakhry C (2018b) Oropharyngeal cancer is no longer a disease of younger patients and the prognostic advantage of human papillomavirus is attenuated among older patients: analysis of the National Cancer Database. *Oral Oncology* 83: 147–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oraloncology.2018.06.013>
- Roman BR, Aragones A (2021) Epidemiology and incidence of HPV-related cancers of the head and neck. *Journal of Surgical Oncology* 124(5): 920–922. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jso.26595>
- Schache AG, Powell NG, Cuschieri KS, Robinson M, Leary S, Mehanna H, Rapozo D, Long A, Cubie H, Junor E, Monaghan H, Harrington KJ, Nutting CM, Schick U, Lau AS, Upile N, Sheard J, Brougham K, West CM, Oguejiofor K, Thomas S, Ness AR, Pring M, Thomas GJ, King EV, McCance DJ, James JA, Moran M, Sloan P, Shaw RJ, Evans M, Jones TM (2016) HPV-related oropharynx cancer in the United Kingdom: An evolution in the understanding of disease etiology. *Cancer Research* 76(22): 6598–6606. <https://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-16-0633>
- Smeets SJ, Hesselink AT, Speel EJ, Haesevoets A, Snijders PJ, Pawlita M, Meijer CJ, Braakhuis BJ, Leemans CR, Brakenhoff RH (2007) A novel algorithm for reliable detection of human papillomavirus in paraffin-embedded head and neck cancer specimens. *International Journal of Cancer* 121(11): 2465–2472. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.22980>
- Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Laversanne M, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A, Bray F (2021) Global cancer statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians* 71(3): 209–249. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21660>
- Tang KD, Vasani S, Menezes L, Taheri T, Walsh LJ, Hughes BGM, Frazer IH, Kenny L, Scheper GC, Punyadeera C (2020) Oral HPV16 DNA as a screening tool to detect early oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma. *Cancer Science* 111(10): 3854–3861. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cas.14585>
- Tsentemeidou A, Fyrmpas G, Stavarakas M, Vlachtsis K, Sotiriou E, Poutoglidis A, Tsetsos N (2021) Human papillomavirus vaccine to end oropharyngeal cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sexually Transmitted Diseases* 48(9): 700–707. <https://doi.org/10.1097/OLQ.0000000000001405>
- Van Dyne EA, Henley SJ, Saraiya M, Thomas CC, Markowitz LE, Benard VB (2018) Trends in human papillomavirus-associated cancers in the United States, 1999–2015. *MMWR Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report* 67(33): 918–924. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm6733a2>
- van Houten VM, Snijders PJ, van den Brekel MW, Kummer JA, Meijer CJ, van Leeuwen B, Denkers F, Smeele LE, Snow GB, Brakenhoff RH (2001) Biological evidence that human papillomaviruses are etiologically involved in a subgroup of head and neck squamous cell carcinomas. *International Journal of Cancer* 93(2): 232–235. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.1313>
- Windon MJ, D'Souza G, Rettig EM, Westra WH, van Zante A, Wang SJ, Ryan WR, Mydlarz WK, Ha PK, Miles BA, Koch W, Gourin C, Eisele DW, Fakhry C (2018) Increasing prevalence of human papillomavirus-positive oropharyngeal cancers among older adults. *Cancer* 124(14): 2993–3001. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.31385>
- Wakeham K, Pan J, Pollock KG, Millan D, Bell S, McLellan D, McPhaden A, Conway DI, Graham SV, Kavanagh K, Cuschieri K (2019) A prospective cohort study of human papillomavirus-driven oropharyngeal cancers: implications for prognosis and immunisation. *Clinical Oncology* 31(9): e132–e142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clon.2019.05.010>
- Yete S, D'Souza W, Saranath D (2018) High-risk human papillomavirus in oral cancer: clinical implications. *Oncology* 94(3): 133–141. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000485471>